

Monitoring spontaneous breathing during apnea testing with electrical impedance tomography

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Abstract: The apnea test (AT) is a critical procedure in the determination of brain death (BD), with the detection of spontaneous breathing efforts serving as a key criterion. However, the reliance on visual observation alone for this assessment can pose challenges in detecting subtle respiratory movements. This case report presents the integration of electrical impedance tomography (EIT) as an adjunctive monitoring tool during the AT in a BD patient, demonstrating its potential to provide real-time visualization of ventilation distribution and detect changes in lung volume. The findings suggest that EIT could enhance the sensitivity and accuracy of detecting spontaneous breathing efforts, offering additional insights into respiratory status of the patient.

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I. Introduction

The apnea test (AT) is essential for confirming brain death (BD). BD can result from various causes, such as severe hypoxemia, impaired perfusion, or toxic neuronal injury, leading to brain anoxia [1]. Detecting the absence of spontaneous breathing effort, controlled by the ventrolateral medulla oblongata, is a key component of BD confirmation [2]. The AT involves increasing the partial pressure of carbon dioxide (PaCO₂) to stimulate the medullary respiratory centers, with a threshold set at 60 mm Hg or an increase of 20 mm Hg above baseline [3].

During the AT, the patient is temporarily disconnected from mechanical ventilation and oxygen is provided via a cannula in the endotracheal tube [3]. This procedure typically lasts 8-10 minutes, with monitoring for respiratory effort, which can be minimal and difficult to observe [2]. A negative AT, indicating brain death, shows no respiratory effort in response to elevated PaCO₂ levels. Conversely, any spontaneous respiratory activity suggests residual brainstem function [3].

Given the challenges in detecting subtle respiratory efforts through visual observation alone, there is a need for enhanced monitoring techniques. Electrical Impedance Tomography (EIT), a non-invasive imaging modality, offers real-time monitoring of ventilation distribution and lung volume changes [4]. Increasingly used in critical care, EIT has the potential to improve sensitivity in detecting

minimal respiratory movements and provide detailed information about lung status during the AT.

II. Case study

A 55-year-old man with a history of hypertension, congestive heart failure, atrial fibrillation, diabetes, and coronary heart disease presented with an intracranial hemorrhage and progressed to BD. He was comatose with a Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) score of 2T/10T (E1-VT-M1). His pupils were dilated and unresponsive to light. His corneal, eyelash, vestibulo-ocular, and cough reflexes were absent. The patient had a heart rate of 83/min, a diastolic blood pressure (DBP) of 55 mm Hg, and a systolic blood pressure (SBP) of 95 mm Hg, resulting in a mean arterial pressure (MAP) of 69 mm Hg.

Figure 1: EIT monitoring results as average tidal images for the patient during the five monitoring signal sections.

The AT was scheduled during the hospital stay. Before the test, the patient was preoxygenated with 100% oxygen for 10 minutes. Baseline arterial blood gas (ABG) measurements showed a pH of 7.40, PaCO₂ of 36.7 mm Hg, and PaO₂ of 529.1 mm Hg. During the AT, oxygen was

administered at a flow rate of 6 L/min through a cannula inserted into the endotracheal tube. EIT measurements were conducted using an electrode belt (Dräger AG, Lübeck, Germany) positioned at the fifth intercostal space, and data were recorded with a PulmoVista 500 (Dräger AG, Lübeck, Germany) at a frame rate of 50 Hz.

After approximately 4 minutes, spontaneous respiratory movements were observed, prompting the abortion of the AT. The patient was reconnected to the ventilator and underwent a recruitment process.

The EIT monitoring period was divided into five signal sections: (a) preoxygenation, (b) apnea test, (c) spontaneous breathing, (d) ventilator reconnected, and (e) recruitment. The monitoring results are displayed in Fig. 1 as tidal images, representing the tidal variation between end-inspiratory and end-expiratory EIT images. These images indicate that during the AT, tidal variation was primarily in the ventral lungs due to the oxygen flow. Spontaneous breathing showed increased tidal variation in the ventral lungs, while mechanical ventilation extended tidal variation to the dorsal lungs, with the largest variation during recruitment.

Figure 2: Horizontal divisions of the regions of interest (ROIs).

Each tidal image was divided into four equal horizontal regions of interest (ROI), as depicted in Fig. 2. Stacked bar charts illustrate tidal variation across these ROIs as illustrated in Fig. 3. This confirms that during the AT and spontaneous breathing, tidal variation occurred mostly in ROI 2 (ventral lungs), with no significant variation in ROI 4 (dorsal lungs). The average total tidal variation during spontaneous breathing and after reconnecting the ventilator was similar. The center of ventilation (CoV), which is depicted in Fig. 3, indicated a shift towards the ventral lungs during the AT. With the onset of spontaneous breathing, ventilation distribution began shifting towards the dorsal lungs, though CoV remained lower than that during mechanical ventilation support.

III. Discussion

In this case report, we explore the use of EIT as an additional tool for detecting spontaneous breathing during the AT in a BD patient. It indicates that EIT detected significantly greater tidal variation during spontaneous breathing compared to the apnea test and revealed a shift in ventilation distribution during spontaneous breathing. Additionally, lung de-recruitment was observed at the initiation of the AT.

The AT aims to induce hypercarbia and respiratory acidosis to stimulate the medullary respiratory centers, which can lead to complications such as cardiac arrhythmias, hypotension, and hypoxemia [2]. Various procedural

modifications, including enhanced monitoring techniques and extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (ECMO), have been explored to mitigate these risks [2, 3]. However, the detection of spontaneous respiratory efforts still primarily relies on visual observation.

Figure 3: Tidal variation across four ROIs and center of ventilation (CoV) variation.

Our case study suggests integrating EIT as a supplementary monitoring technique during the AT. EIT provides continuous, real-time imaging of ventilation distribution, offering quantitative data that can enhance the detection of subtle respiratory movements which can be missed by visual observation alone.

Despite its potential, this study has limitations. Standardized protocols and comprehensive clinician training are required for effective EIT integration into clinical practice. Although EIT has proven useful in other critical care contexts, its specific application to the AT in BD determination needs further evaluation to assess its practicality and effectiveness.

In conclusion, this preliminary case study suggests that EIT could be a valuable supplementary tool for detecting spontaneous respiratory efforts during the AT. Further large-scale studies are needed to validate these findings and address the practical aspects of incorporating EIT into the clinical workflow for BD patient monitoring during the AT.

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AUTHOR'S STATEMENT

This study was approved by the Human Investigation Review Board of the University of Szeged with approval number 87/2020-SZTE. The trial was pre-registered on ClinicalTrials.gov under NCT04857242. Informed consent has been obtained from all individuals included in this study. The research related to human use complies with all the relevant national regulations and institutional policies and was performed in accordance with the tenets of the Helsinki Declaration.

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